

Reversal of Charge of Serum and its Coagulation and Gelatinisation with Acids.

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In a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 818) the authors have shown that polyvalent cations and acids possess high coagulating powers towards serum and that dilution stabilises serum against coagulation by univalent ions derived from salts like sodium acetate, potassium fluoride, oxalate, etc. While the normal dilution effect has been observed when serum is coagulated by acids and polyvalent cations, marked ionic antagonism is developed when it is coagulated by the cations of varying valencies or an acid and a salt. The phenomenon of positive acclimatisation is more marked for the diluted serum than the concentrated one when coagulated by salts, while with acids, the phenomenon is less developed with dilute serum. We have shown that like the sols of gamboge, mastic, arsenious sulphide, etc., serum is also capable of adsorbing similarly charged ions when coagulated with electrolytes.

In the present investigation, we have found that there are two distinct points of coagulation for serum, one with dilute and the other with concentrated acids. The gelatinisation of serum by acids has also been studied.

Goat blood was collected in a glass vessel in which it clotted within a few minutes. The clear straw-coloured serum which was squeezed out due to syneresis was used.

Two c. c. of original serum were made up to 10 c. c. with different concentrations of dilute or concentrated acid and the requisite amount of water; the coagulation was observed after one hour.

TABLE I.

Concentrations in normality of dilute and concentrated acids are shown in columns I and II respectively.

Acids.	I	II	Acids.	I	II
HCl	0.0029	0.275	Cl ₂ COOH	0.0034	0.0848
HNO ₃	0.0034	0.0899	HCOOH	0.0036	5.9454
H ₂ SO ₄	0.0024	0.1161	CH ₃ COOH	0.0038	2.8458
CH ₃ ClCOOH	0.0024	0.6864	H ₃ PO ₄	0.0033	0.6804

The effect of dilution of serum on coagulation with concentrated acids has also been investigated.

A/2 serum=1 c. c. of serum. A serum=2 c. c. of serum.
 2A serum=4 c.c. of serum. Total volume=10 c. c. Time=1 hour.

TABLE II.

Acids.	Volume in c. c. necessary for coagulation.		
	A/2	A	2A
1.75N-HCl	1.6	1.3	1.0
0.741N-HNO ₃	1.5	1.2	0.6
1.452N-H ₂ SO ₄	1.4	0.8	0.55
4.896N-CH ₃ COOH	2.3	1.4	0.6
0.174N-CCl ₃ COOH	2.4	2.0	1.4
22.02N-HCOOH	3.6	2.7	1.3
15.81N-CH ₃ COOH	3.2	1.8	1.0
7.88N-H ₃ PO ₄	1.3	0.8	0.45

From the results recorded above, it will be seen that for the second point of coagulation, much higher concentrations of acids are necessary than for the first point; and when the serum is coagulated by concentrated acids, it behaves abnormally towards dilution, due to its marked tendency of adsorbing similarly charged ions from the acids. It has been found (*loc. cit.*) that for the first point of coagulation by dilute acids, the serum behaves normally towards dilution, and smaller amounts of acids are necessary to coagulate the dilute serum than the concentrated one.

Serum is not coagulated even by molar solutions of ammonium sulphate; its globulin content is only precipitated out when it is half saturated with the salt. The results recorded in the following table show that in presence of small quantities of acids, serum is sensitised and is easily coagulated by ammonium sulphate. When the amount of hydrochloric acid added to the serum is small, the serum becomes unstable towards ammonium sulphate. This behaviour has been explained on the assumption that in presence of small amounts of acid, the hydrolysis of serum is checked and thus it is made unstable. Similar results have been obtained with the sols of Prussian blue, copper ferrocyanide, arsenious sulphide, gamboge, mastic and gum dammar (compare *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 830; *Kolloid Z.*, 1926, 29, 346).

TABLE III.

Amount of serum = 2 c. c. Total volume = 10 c. c. Time = 1 hour.
 Volume in c. c. of 1.75N-Hydrochloric acid added. Volume c. c. of M/10-Ammonium sulphate necessary for coagulation.

1.3	0
0	more than 5 c. c. of 2M
0.2	0.8
0.3	1.7
0.4	2.6
0.5	1.6

From these results, it appears that as the concentration of hydrochloric acid is increased, the serum becomes more and more stabilised by the adsorption of hydrogen ions, and evidently there is a reversal of the charge on the serum, which becomes positive on account of the adsorption of hydrogen ions. With higher concentrations of acids, both cations and anions influence the coagulation points, and the positively charged serum is coagulated by anions. The marked tendency of adsorbing similarly charged hydrogen ions by the positively reversed serum is shown from the fact that dilute serum is more stable towards coagulation by concentrated acids than concentrated serum.

Serum contains, besides other substances, two proteins, *vis.*, serum albumin and serum globulin, and it has long been known that serum globulin is precipitated when it is half saturated with ammonium sulphate, but serum albumin is only obtained when the filtrate after removing globulins is saturated with ammonium sulphate and acidified with 10% acetic acid (resulting solution containing 1% acetic acid) and allowed to stand for two hours or longer. The addition of acetic acid for the precipitation of albumin by ammonium sulphate is in accord with the view just stated and it appears that on the addition of sufficient quantity of acids, a reversal in the charge of serum takes place, which helps its coagulation by multivalent anions.

It appears that in these coagulation experiments on serum, the whole of the colloidal phase is never completely precipitated. When serum is coagulated by dilute acids or by sodium acetate, tartrate, citrate, etc., it is mainly the globulin portion which is thrown down as is the case when it is half saturated with ammonium sulphate. But serum albumin is also precipitated when coagulation is carried by either concentrated acids or salts with polyvalent cations. Two distinct points of coagulation as with acids are also obtained when serum is coagulated by such electrolytes as aluminium nitrate, cerous nitrate, thorium nitrate, copper sulphate, etc.

The coagulation of serum by acids appears to be mainly controlled by hydrogen-ion concentrations. In the following table, we are recording the variation in pH values with different amounts of acids, pH values were determined by indicator method, using nitrophenols as indicators. Original serum had a $pH=7.8$. On diluting serum with water, an opalescent solution is obtained and on the addition of dilute acids, turbidity at first increases corresponding to the first coagulation point, but after a certain concentration, the solution begins to clear indicating the beginning of the reversal of charge and on further addition of the electrolytes, quite transparent serum is obtained when the charge reversal is complete.

Original serum $\rightarrow pH=7.8$.

2 C. c. of serum + 8 c. c. water $\rightarrow pH=7.6$.

2 C. c. of serum were mixed with different concentrations of *N*-10 acids and the total volume was made up to 10 c. c. The hydrogen-ion concentrations are recorded in the following table.

TABLE IV.

Volume, in c. c. of <i>N</i> /10 acid.	Hydro. chloric acid.	Nitric acid.	Sulphuric acid.	Mono chlor-acetic acid.	Tri chlor-acetic acid.	Formic acid.
	pH	pH	pH	pH	pH	pH
0.1	7.8	7.3	7.3	7.5	7.5	7.8
0.3	6.8A	6.9A	7.0A	7.15A	6.9A	6.9A
0.5	6.0	6.2	6.3	6.6	6.2	6.4
0.6	—	—	6.1	—	—	—
0.7	5.6B	5.6B	6.7	6.1	5.7	6.0
0.9	—	—	5.6	—	—	—
1.0	5.4	5.5	5.4	5.4	5.3	5.4
1.1	5.3	—	—	—	4.9B	—
1.2	5.2C	5.3C	5.3B	5.3B	4.7	5.3B
1.4	—	4.9	4.9	5.2	4.4C	5.3
1.5	4.0	—	—	—	—	—
1.6	—	—	4.6	5.0C	4.4	5.3
1.8	—	—	4.3C	4.7	—	5.3C
2.0	—	—	4.0	—	—	5.1

From A to B—Region of first coagulation point.

At B—Opalescence begins to disappear and reversal of charge begins.

At C—Reversal of charge is complete.

From the above table it will be seen that the charge reversal takes place in almost the same region for different acids.

TABLE V.

Acids.	Charge reversal region.	Acids.	Charge reversal region.
HCl	pH 5.5—5.3	CH ₃ COOH	pH 5.3—5.0
HNO ₃	5.6—5.3	CCl ₃ COOH	4.9—4.4
H ₂ SO ₄	5.3—4.3	HCOOH	5.3

From this it will be seen that the conditions most favorable for the charge reversal of serum are near the pH 5.3—5.0. As has already been stated that the dissolution of the turbid phase was taken as an indication of the reversal of charge, some allowance has to be made in the measurements where the anion effects are more marked as in the case of sulphuric acid, where due to the coagulating influence of SO₄ ions on the positively charged serum, the turbidity did not disappear till it had reached the pH 4.8. Thus it appears that the coagulation of serum by dilute acids is mainly a function of hydrogen-ion concentrations, and anions exert only a secondary influence.

The coagulating power of concentrated acids for the second point as seen from Table I is in the following order:—

Trichloroacetic > nitric > sulphuric > hydrochloric > hypophosphorous > monochloroacetic > acetic > formic. From this it appears that the degree of dissociation of the acids influence the coagulation of serum markedly so far as the second coagulation point is concerned.

The two coagulation points of serum also affect the hydration tendency of particles differently in the two cases. From the nature of the coagulated mass it appears that serum coagulated by dilute acids is more flocculent than gelatinous. After the reversal of charge, further coagulation is accompanied by marked adsorption of the solvent medium, and the viscosity of the system also gradually increases, and finally under suitable concentrations, stable jellies of the serum are obtained. It appears that serum albumin which has a greater probability of being precipitated near the second coagulation point, is more liable of hydration than the serum globulin which is exclusively precipitated by dilute acids.

In the following tables, observations on gelatinisation of serum by different acids are recorded. A certain volume of serum mixed and well-shaken with different amounts of acids was made up to 5 c.c. in every case with the requisite amount of water and the time of setting to jellies was noted.

TABLE VI.

Gelatinisation by Hydrochloric Acid.

3 C.c. of serum mixed with varying amounts of HCl and the total volume made up to 5 c.c.

1.75N-HCl.	Observation.	1.75N-HCl.	Observation.
1.0 c.c.	No jelly in 2 days.	1.6 c.c.	Opaque jelly in 22 hrs.
1.2	No jelly in 2 days.	1.8	Opaque jelly in 3 hrs.
1.4	Opaque jelly in 22 hrs.	2.0	Flocculent precipitate ₂ setting to loose jelly within 22 hrs.

TABLE VII.

Gelatinisation by Nitric, Sulphuric and Trichloroacetic Acids.

Serum can also be gelatinised by other strong acids, such as nitric, sulphuric, and trichloroacetic, like hydrochloric acid, and the jellies thus obtained are mostly opaque.

Total volume = 5 c.c.

Vol. of serum (c.c.).	Volume of acids (c.c.)			Time of gelation.
	2.965N-HNO ₃ .	7.26N-H ₂ SO ₄ .	0.879N-CCl ₃ COOH.	
3	0.1—0.3	—	0.1—0.3	No jelly.
	—	0.8	—	Jelly within 1 day.
	0.4	1.1—1.4	0.4	Within 3 to 7 hours.
4	0.6	—	0.5—0.6	Within 10 minutes.
	0.2	—	0.3—0.4	No jelly.
	—	0.4—0.6	—	Jelly in 1 day.
	—	0.8—1.0	—	Within 4 to 6 hours.
4.5	0.3—0.4	—	0.5	Within 1 to 4 hours.
	0.5	—	0.6	Within $\frac{1}{2}$ hour.
	—	—	0.4—0.5	No jelly.
	0.2	0.2—0.5	—	Jelly within 1 day.
	0.3	—	—	Within $3\frac{1}{2}$ hours.
	0.4	—	—	Within 25 minutes.

TABLE VIII.

Gelatinisation by Acetic Acid.

Total Vol. = 5 c.c.

Vol. of serum.	Vol. of 15.81 N-acetic acid (glacial).	Observation.
3 c.c.	0.5 c.c.	No jelly in 1 day.
3	1.0	Translucent jelly in 40 mins.
3	1.5	Opaque jelly in 3 mins.
3	2.0	Opaque jelly in 2 mins.
4	0.1	No jelly in 1 day.
4	0.4	Translucent jelly in 3 days.
4	0.7	Translucent jelly in 45 mins.
4	1.0	Translucent jelly in 3 mins.
4.5	0.1	No jelly in 1 day.
4.5	0.3	No jelly in 1 day.
4.5	0.5	Translucent jelly in 1 day.

TABLE IX.

Gelatinisation by Monochloroacetic Acid.

Vol. of serum (c.c.).	Total vol.=5 c.c.	
	Vol. of 4.896-N. CH ₂ ClCOOH. (c.c.).	Observation.
3	0.8	No jelly.
3	0.6	Translucent jelly in 1 day.
3	0.9	Translucent jelly in 1 hr.
3	1.2	Opaque jelly in 25 mins.
4	0.4	Translucent jelly in 1 day.
4	0.6	Translucent jelly in 2½ hrs.
4	0.8	Translucent jelly in 25 mins.
4	1.0	Loose translucent jelly in 1 day.
4.5	0.8	Translucent jelly in 1 day.
4.5	0.4	Translucent jelly in 1 day.
4.5	0.5	Translucent jelly in 3 hrs.

TABLE X.

Gelatinisation by Formic Acid.

Vol. of serum (c.c.).	Total vol.=5 c.c.	
	Vol. of 22.02 N- formic acid (c.c.).	Observation.
3	0.4	No jelly in 1 day.
3	0.6	No jelly in 1 day.
3	0.8	Translucent jelly in 1 day.
4	0.4	No jelly in 1 day.
4	0.6	Translucent jelly in 3½ hrs.
4	0.8	Translucent jelly in 20 mins.
4	1.0	Translucent jelly in 3 mins.
4.5	0.1	No jelly in 1 day.
4.5	0.3	No jelly in 1 day.
4.5	0.5	Translucent jelly in 2½ hrs.

TABLE XI

Gelatinisation by Oxalic Acid.

No jelly could be obtained by using even saturated solution of oxalic acid. However, jellies could be prepared by shaking serum with solid oxalic acids and allowing it to set.

Total vol. = 5 c.c.		
Vol. of serum (c.c.).	Amount of solid oxalic acid (g.).	Observation.
3	0.9	No jelly even in 3 days.
3	1.1	No jelly even in 3 days.
3	1.3	Translucent jelly in 3 days.
4	0.7	Loose translucent jelly in 1 day.
4	0.9	Loose translucent jelly in 1 day.
4	1.1	Firm translucent jelly in 1 day.
4	1.3	Firm translucent jelly in 1 day.
4.5	0.5	Opaque jelly in 1 day.
4.5	0.7	Opaque jelly in 1 day.
4.5	0.9	Opaque loose jelly in 1 day.

TABLE XII.

Gelatinisation by Hypophosphorous Acid.

Total vol. = 5 c.c.		
Vol. of serum (c.c.).	Vol. of 7.869 N-hypophosphorous acid (c.c.).	Observation.
3	0.5	No jelly in 1 day.
3	0.8	No jelly in 1 day.
3	1.1	Translucent jelly in 1 day.
3	1.4	Opaque jelly in 1 day.
4	0.4	No jelly in 1 day.
4	0.6	No jelly in 1 day.
4	0.8	Translucent jelly in 1 day.
4	1.0	Translucent jelly in 4½ hrs.
4.5	0.3	No jelly in 1 day.
4.5	0.4	No jelly in 1 day.
4.5	0.5	Translucent jelly in 1 day.

TABLE XIII.

Gelatinisation by Aluminium Nitrats.

Vol. of serum (c.c.).	Total vol. = 5 c.c. Vol. of M/1-27- aluminium nitrate (c.c.).	Observation.
3	0.5	No jelly.
3	1.0	Opaque jelly in 1 day.
3	1.5	Opaque jelly in 1 hr.
3	2.0	Opaque loose jelly immediately.
4	0.8	No jelly.
4	1.0	Opaque jelly in 1 day.
4.5	0.8	Opaque jelly in 1 day.

It will be seen from these tables that the jellies of the best texture are obtained by using weak acids. Glacial acetic, formic, monochloroacetic, hypophosphorous and oxalic acids yield almost transparent jellies, while strong acids such as hydrochloric, sulphuric nitric and trichloroacetic acids yield opaque jellies. Salts containing polyvalent cations, like aluminium nitrate also give opaque jellies. These jellies are very stable; they do not undergo any marked syneresis, though putrefaction begins after a couple of days. An attempt to gelatinise serum by very weak acids like citric, tartaric and phosphoric acids has been so far unsuccessful. It appears that it is partly due to the weak nature of these acids and partly due to the fact that their solutions cannot be obtained in such concentrations as those of formic and acetic acids. The gelatinisation of serum appears to be a function of hydrogen ion concentration. The concentrations of the acids used for this purpose are in the following order:—

Trichloroacetic < nitric < sulphuric < hydrochloric < monochloroacetic
< hypophosphorous < acetic < formic.

This order generally agrees with that of concentrated acids, in similar experiments.

We have already shown that serum behaves abnormally towards dilution when coagulated by concentrated acids. Our results on gelatinisation of serum, also show that with increased concentration of serum, the amount of acid required to produce a jelly in a definite time decreases, that is, much less acid is required to produce a jelly with concentrated serum than with dilute one.

Summary.

1. It has been observed that there are two distinct points of coagulation, when serum is coagulated by acids or salts of polyvalent cations. The first point is obtained by using zilute acids, and the second by concentrated acids.

2. The coagulating power of concentrated acids for the second point is in the following order: —

Trichloroacetic > nitric > sulphuric > hydrochloric > hypophosphorous > monochloroacetic > acetic > formic.

3. When serum is coagulated by concentrated acids, it behaves abnormally towards dilution, as it has a high tendency of absorbing similarly charged ions from the acids.

4. It has been shown that in the presence of small quantities of acids, serum is sensitised, and is easily coagulated by ammonium sulphate. This is partly due to the fact that the hydrolysis of serum is checked by acids and partly because the charge on serum is reversed by the adsorption of hydrogen ions.

5. It has been shown that charge reversal of serum takes place near p_4 5.8-5.0, when serum is coagulated by acids. It is the globulin portion of serum which is exclusively precipitated by dilute acids near the first coagulation point, while at the second coagulation point, serum albumin is also thrown down.

6. When serum is coagulated by dilute acids, the precipitated mass is flocculent, while with concentrated acids, a gelatinous mass is obtained. Under suitable concentrations of acids, jellies of serum can also be obtained.

7. Very stable translucent jellies of serum undergoing no marked syneresis are obtained when serum is coagulated by concentrated solutions of acetic, monochloroacetic, formic and hypophosphorous acids and solid oxalic acid. Hydrochloric, nitric, sulphuric and trichloroacetic acids yield opaque stable jellies of serum.

8. The concentrations of acids necessary for the preparation of jellies are in the following order: —

Trichloroacetic < nitric < sulphuric < hydrochloric < monochloroacetic < hypophosphorous < acetic < formic.

9. As the concentration of serum increases, the amount of acid required to gelatinise serum in a definite time decreases.

Thiodiazines. Part VI.

BY PRAFULLA KUMAR BOSE AND BIRENDRA KUMAR NANDI.

While studying the action of phenylthiocarbohydrazide upon ω -bromoacetophenone, Guha and Ray-Choudhury (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 153) made the assumption that the -CO- group of the bromo-ketone first acted on the hydrazino-residue of the hydrazide leading to the formation of the intermediate compound (I, type *a*),

which finally lost hydrogen bromide to give the thiodiazine (II). The mechanism proposed above by Guha and Ray-Choudhury is different from what one of us suggested (Bose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 51) and consequently it was deemed necessary to study the subject further.

The isolation of a compound (III, type *a*) or (IV, type *b*) from the product of interaction of ω -bromoacetophenone and a thiosemicarbazide would have definitely settled this point. But this was unsuccessful (Part I). It has however been pointed out in Part I as well as in Part II of this series (Bose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 100) that varying quantities of thiazoles are formed in the thiodiazine condensation referred to above.

The formation of these can be very easily explained by assuming an intermediate compound of the type (*b*) i.e., (IV). A compound of the type (*a*) can never give rise to a thiazole derivative directly by elimination of hydrobromic acid.

Further evidences as to the nature of the intermediates were sought to be gathered from the interaction between a thiosemicarbazide and *p*-methyl- ω -bromo-acetophenone. But unfortunately the results obtained, even under varied conditions, were inconclusive. This reaction was found to lead either to a thiodiazine or to a thiazole and not to both, which is remarkable in view of our previous experiences. Thiodiazines (V) are obtained by using 4-substituted thiosemicarbazides. The constitution of the products was indirectly ascertained by observing the absence of reactivity towards aldehydes and ketones.

A thiodiazole (VI) is obtained using thiosemicarbazide. The constitutional formula of this compound was established by converting it into the monoacetyl and benzylidene derivatives and proving their identity with the corresponding products synthesised from acetyl- and benzylidene-thiosemicarbazides. Any claims to the alternative thiazole formula (VII) for the substance are thus rejected.

The compound (VI) also reacted with isothiocyanates and thiocyanic acid producing additive compounds of the type (VIII) and (IX) respectively. The latter again could be condensed with a further molecule of *p*-methyl- ω -bromo-acetophenone yielding (X). This was prepared in connexion with another investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Keto-4-p-tolyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazolehydrasone (VI).

Thiosemicarbazide (one mol., 1 g.) and *p*-methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone (1 mol., 2.3 g.) were shaken with 35 c.c. of absolute alcohol. The reactants gradually passed into solution with development of heat. After a few minutes a precipitate separated out. To ensure the completion of the reaction the whole thing was heated on a water-bath under reflux for 15-20 minutes. The mixture was cooled and diluted with ether. The crude crystalline hydrobromide of the base (2.4 g.) was collected, washed thoroughly with ether and dried on a porous plate.

To obtain the free base, the hydrobromide was dissolved in boiling dilute hydrochloric acid when most of the solid went into solution. A little tarry matter and some solid remained undissolved. These were filtered off while hot and the filtrate was neutralised with a dilute solution of sodium carbonate when the solution turned milky, and shortly afterwards needle-shaped crystals appeared. These were collected, redissolved in hot dilute hydrochloric acid, filtered, and again precipitated with sodium carbonate solution (yield, 1.2 g.). When crystallised from methyl alcohol in colourless needles, it melted at 178°. (Found: C, 58.39; H, 5.28; N, 20.55. $C_{10}H_{11}N_3S$ requires C, 58.54; H, 5.37; N, 20.49 per cent.).

The base is soluble in ethyl alcohol, benzene and pyridine but crystallises best from methyl alcohol. On exposure to air it gradually turns brown owing to atmospheric oxidation.

The *hydrochloride* was obtained by dissolving the base in boiling hydrochloric acid (20%) and allowing the solution to cool. It was recrystallised from alcohol in colourless plates, m.p. 133°. (Found: N, 17.21. $C_{10}H_{12}N_3S \cdot Cl$ requires N, 17.89 per cent.).

The *benzylidene derivative* of (VI) crystallised in colourless needles from absolute alcohol. It is soluble in pyridine and acetone but sparingly so in benzene; m.p. 205°. (Found: N, 14.46. $C_{17}H_{15}N_3S$ requires N, 14.34 per cent.).

Benzylidene thiosemicarbasone and p-Methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone.—The condensation was effected in alcoholic medium as described above using molecular proportions. The free base was precipitated from the solution by adding a little pyridine and water, and was finally crystallised from alcohol. The m.p. of this base alone or when mixed with the above product was found to be 205°.

2-Keto-4-p-tolyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole-isopropylidenehydrazone was obtained by heating the base with acetone under reflux for about half an hour. On dilution with water a precipitate was formed which was crystallised from alcohol in very pale yellow crystals melting at 230°. (Found: N, 17·22. $C_{13}H_{15}N_3S$ requires N, 17·14 per cent.).

The *benzoyl* derivative crystallised in needle-shaped colourless crystals from alcohol, m.p. 201°. (Found: N, 18·71. $C_{17}H_{15}ON_3S$ requires N, 18·58 per cent.).

The *acetyl derivative* of (VI) was prepared by heating the base, 2-keto-4-p-tolyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazolehydrazone, with acetic anhydride and a little pyridine for about 25 minutes. It separated in colourless, long needles from methyl alcohol, m.p. 195°. (Found: N, 17·08. $C_{12}H_{13}ON_3S$ requires N, 17·00 per cent.). It is soluble in alcohol and benzene. The compound is very stable and does not, like the free base, change colour when exposed to the atmosphere.

Condensation of 1-Acetylthiosemicarbazide and Methyl- ω -bromo-p-acetophenone.—The condensation product was obtained by heating acetylthiosemicarbazide (2 g.) and *p*-methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone (2·3 g.) in alcohol (30 c.c.) for a few minutes. The substance crystallised from absolute alcohol in colourless, long needles, m.p. 195°. It dissolved in warm alkali and was found to be identical with the acetyl derivative described above.

2-Keto-4-p-tolyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazolethiosemicarbazone (IX).—To 100 c.c. of dry absolute alcohol containing 0·9 g. of dry hydrochloric acid gas, 5 g. of the base (VI) and 3 g. (excess) of potassium sulphocyanide were added and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 6–7 hours. The potassium chloride obtained on cooling the reaction mixture was filtered off and the filtrate, on concentration, deposited crystals which were recrystallised in beautiful glistening plates (pinkish) from absolute alcohol. It melts at 218° and is soluble in most organic media. (Found: N, 21·37. $C_{11}H_{12}N_4S$ requires N, 21·27 per cent.).

2-Keto-4-p-tolyl-2:3-dihydrothiazolethiosemicarbazone and p-Methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone: Formation of (X).—The thiosemicarbazone (0·5 g.) dissolved in absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) was thoroughly shaken with *p*-methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone (0·4 g.) for some time at the ordinary temperature and finally heated under reflux on a water-bath for a few minutes. The condensation product which separated

was collected. For purification it was extracted with hot dilute hydrochloric acid, and the extract made alkaline with a dilute solution of sodium carbonate when the product crystallised out. This was recrystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 120°. (Found: N, 14·39. $C_{20}H_{18}N_4S_2$ requires N, 14·82 per cent.).

2-Keto-4-p-tolyl-2 : 8-dihydro-1 : 3-thiazole-4-methylthiosemicarbazone (VIII, R = CH_3).—To an alcoholic solution of compound (VI) methyl isothiocyanate was added drop by drop. On slight warming and then cooling a precipitate appeared. This was crystallised from methyl alcohol in yellowish needles, m.p. 146°. (Found: N, 19·93. $C_{12}H_{14}N_4S_2$ requires N, 20·14 per cent.).

Similar additive products were obtained with *phényl*-, *o*-tolyl- and *p*-tolyl-isothiocyanates. The *phényl* derivative (from alcohol) had m.p. 191°. (Found: N, 16·39. $C_{17}H_{16}N_4S_2$ requires N, 16·47 per cent.).

The *o*-tolyl-derivative formed slightly pink needles from alcohol, m.p. 174°, soluble in alcohol, ether, benzene and acetone. (Found: N, 16·10. $C_{18}H_{18}N_4S_2$ requires N, 15·82 per cent.).

The *p*-tolyl-derivative was a pale yellow crystalline substance (from alcohol), m.p. 166°. (Found: N, 15·88. $C_{18}H_{18}N_4S_2$ requires N, 15·82 per cent.).

2-Methylamino-5-p-tolyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine (V, R = CH_3).—To 4-methylthiosemicarbazide (2 g.) dissolved in 30 c.c. of absolute alcohol, *p*-methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone (4·1 g.) was added. The reaction was completed by heating under reflux for 15 minutes. The hydrobromide of the base separated in yellow clusters. These were filtered off and the free base separated as described before.

The base crystallised in colourless needles from alcohol and melted at 249°. It is soluble in alcohol, pyridine and benzene, but insoluble in ether. (Found: N, 19·00. $C_{11}H_{13}N_3S$ requires N, 19·17 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* of the base crystallised from dilute alcohol (60 per cent.) in colourless plates, m.p. 195°. (Found: N, 16·20. $C_{11}H_{14}N_3S \cdot Cl$ requires N, 16·07 per cent.).

4-isoButylthiosemicarbazide, $C_4H_9NH \cdot CS \cdot NH \cdot NH_2$.—Hydrazine hydrate (5 g.) was dissolved in 20 c.c. of absolute alcohol and the solution cooled in ice. *iso*Butylisothiocyanate (11·5 g.) was then dropped into the cooled solution with frequent shaking. After a few minutes colourless, silky, glistening crystals appeared. These were filtered off and washed with 10 per cent. alcohol. It

crystallised in beautiful long needles from rectified spirit. It is very soluble in alcohol; m.p. 79° (yield almost quantitative). (Found: N, 28·50. $C_5H_{13}N_3S$ requires N, 28·57 per cent.).

The *benzylidene* derivative, $C_4H_9NH\cdot CS\cdot NH\cdot N\cdot CHPh$, which was easily prepared in alcoholic medium, formed colourless silky needles, m.p. 125°.

The *isopropylidene* derivative, $C_4H_9NH\cdot CS\cdot NH\cdot N\cdot CMe_2$ was prepared by boiling the substance with acetone for a few minutes. It formed silky plates, m.p. 112°.

2-isoButylamino-5-p-tolyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine (V, R=isobutyl).—*4-isoButylthiosemicarbazide* (3 g.) dissolved in 30 c.c. of absolute alcohol was treated with *p*-methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone (4·4 g.): the mixture was shaken, and finally heated on a water-bath for 25 minutes. On cooling, yellow clusters appeared which increased on the addition of ether to the solution. The hydrobromide was collected, and the base liberated as usual by dilute sodium carbonate. The crude brownish precipitate was crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in colourless needles, m.p. 159°. It is soluble in benzene, pyridine and acetone. (Found: C, 64·15; H, 7·35; N, 16·00. $C_{14}H_{19}N_3S$ requires C, 64·36; H, 7·27; N, 16·09 per cent.). The base turns brown on standing in air, especially when moist.

The *hydrochloride* crystallised in colourless leaflets from alcohol having m.p. 125°. (Found: N, 14·18. $C_{14}H_{20}N_3S\cdot Cl$ requires N, 14·11 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from alcohol in light yellow crystals, m.p. 167°. (Found: N, 13·78. $C_{16}H_{21}ON_3S$ requires N, 13·86 per cent.).

2-Phenylamino-5-p-tolyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine (V, R=Ph).—From 3 g. *4-phenylthiosemicarbazide* in 50 c.c. of absolute alcohol and 3·8 g. *p*-methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone, 1·8 g. of the purified base were obtained. It crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles after treatment with charcoal; m.p. 198°. (Found: N, 15·01. $C_{16}H_{15}N_3S$ requires N, 14·94 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* separated from dilute alcohol in colourless plates, m.p. 135°. (Found: N, 13·41. $C_{15}H_{16}N_3S\cdot Cl$ requires N, 13·22 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from absolute alcohol melted at 170°. (Found: N, 13·19. $C_{18}H_{17}ON_3S$ requires N, 13·00 per cent.).

2-o-Tolylamino-5-p-tolyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine (V, R=*o*-tolyl).—It was prepared in a similar way. The free base was obtained in needles, having a slight brownish tint, m.p. 179°. (Found: N, 14.14. $C_{17}H_{17}N_3S$ requires N, 14.24 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* separated in colourless crystals from dilute alcohol, m.p. 171°. (Found: N, 12.48. $C_{17}H_{18}N_3S \cdot Cl$ requires N, 12.66 per cent.)

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised in colourless needles from absolute alcohol in which it was moderately soluble. It melts at 199°. (Found: N, 12.40. $C_{19}H_{19}ON_3S$ requires N, 12.46 per cent.).

2-p-Tolylamino-5-p-tolyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine (V, R=*p*-tolyl) was obtained in the usual manner from 4-*p*-tolylthiosemicarbazide and *p*-methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone. It formed almost colourless prisms, m.p. 187°, from a mixture of ethyl and methyl alcohol (1:1). It is also soluble in pyridine and benzene. (Found: N, 14.29. $C_{17}H_{17}N_3S$ requires N, 14.24 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* was obtained by treating the base with dilute hydrochloric acid and crystallising the product from alcohol, m.p. 199°.

The *acetyl* derivative was obtained in prisms from alcohol; m.p. 154°. (Found: N, 12.50. $C_{19}H_{19}ON_3S$ requires N, 12.46 per cent.)

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